

Agroforestry Practices for Sustainable Livestock Management and Enhancement of Soil Hydrogeological Stability

Evrytania is a mountainous regional unit in Central Greece, characterized by rugged terrain, dense forests, and abundant water resources, where silvopasture in grasslands and forestlands coexist with livestock farming. This unique natural environment requires sustainable management aimed at maintaining vegetation cover, improving soil structure, and enhancing hydrogeological stability.

Agroforestry Practices for Livestock and Hydrogeological Stability

The main agroforestry practices applied in Evrytania include silvopasture including rotational grazing, which contributes to the maintenance of vegetation cover and the prevention of overgrazing, as it allows sufficient time for soils and plants to recover. In addition, the preservation of large trees within grazing areas, as well as the protection of mountainous regions and riparian zones along streams and rivers, constitute key practices of sustainable land management. The presence of forest and shrub species in silvopastoral landscapes provides shade, improves the microclimate, and regulates temperature and soil moisture, enhancing soil biodiversity while offering natural forage and shelter for livestock. At the same time, the root systems of trees and shrubs, both deep and shallow, retain and stabilize the soil, reducing erosion processes, while incorporating organic matter in deep soil layers. Furthermore, the protection of riparian areas through the maintenance of vegetation limits soil losses, increases water

infiltration, and improves water quality, thereby strengthening the hydrological stability of the region.

Figure 1 Silvopasture, Myriki community at the foothills of Mount Tymfristos (Municipality of Karpenisi, Evrytania) (Photo: Galanopoulou S., 2025)

Additional information

Silvopasture practices in Evrytania, where mountainous terrain and increased rainfall dominate, are particularly important to reduce the risk of flooding and landslides. Through the implementation of silvopasture agroforestry practices, traditional livestock farming and the local economy are supported, while at the same time the resilience of the ecosystem is enhanced, and the hydrogeological balance of the area is maintained.

KEYWORDS

mountain livestock farming, erosion, silvopasture agroforestry practices

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